

Customer Satisfaction on Banking Services in Indian Growing Economy Nainital District

Dr. Sanjeev Saxena¹ and Mayank Jindal²

¹Associate Professor, Department of Commerce, MB Government PG College, Haldwani, Uttarakhand, INDIA

²Research Scholar, Department of Commerce, MB Government PG College, Haldwani, Uttarakhand, INDIA

²Corresponding Author: mayankjindal.512@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Finance is the energy of every business whether it is profit making or loss-making business and finance are required. Economy grows with the developing people of his country. There is no way to grow the country economy without financial growing of his resident peoples and banking sector play a major role to provide financial services. Banks play a major role in the growth of the economy by providing their services. Customer satisfaction is essential for the future growth of both bank and country economy growth also. This study made to determine customer satisfaction level on banking services. This study based on primary data. Primary data collected through questionnaire. The questionnaire collected from 50 peoples in Kumoun region specially in Haldwani urban area. All types of people included in sample collection Students, Employees, Self Employees, and retired persons. To assess customer satisfaction used the pre-tested five points Likert's scale test. On the basis of the analysis, it is concluded that the customer service satisfaction level of banks is 73.80%. **Key Words:** Customer satisfaction, Banking services, Overall satisfaction.

Keywords-- Bank Customer Satisfaction, Banking Services, Economic Growth

I. INTRODUCTION

The bank is a financial service institution established with two basic objectives ones accepting deposits and second provide loans. Bank provides services to its customers and customer satisfaction is essential for the future growth of the bank.

Banks play a major role in the growth of the economy by providing their services. Customer satisfaction is essential for the future growth of both bank and country economy growth also. This study made to determine the customer satisfaction level on banking services. Customer is standing on line to wait his number because all banks have to wait for his number on mostly counter. It is create workload on workers of bank and workload negatively change the behavior of bank staff and waiting line also create negative behavior of customers also create unsatisfaction of customer from services.

Customer satisfaction has two dimension one's expectation of customers and second high quality and timely services provided by the bank and both effect influence the customer satisfaction. By this study we will identify the overall customer satisfaction level.

“Customer satisfaction refers to how satisfied the customers are, with the product or service they receive from a particular agency especially banking industry. The banks like other business organization develops innovative sales techniques and advanced marketing tools to gain supremacy namely ATM, Mobile banking, net banking and through banking apps designed for each banks. Now-a-days, banks aim to provide all banking product and service under one roof and their endeavor is to be customer perception and expectation, hence the present study is carried out⁽¹⁾

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Herath H.M.A.K (2019), Bankers and policy makers will be able to understand the level of customer satisfaction regarding different aspects of green initiatives. Most importantly, they will be able to understand the level of impact generated by each category on overall green customer satisfaction. Hence they can decide necessary actions to be done regarding their green initiatives, in order to uplift customer satisfaction on overall green banking. ⁽²⁾

Singh Inder Pal, Bassi Payal (2017), To satisfy the need of the customers, public and private sector banks provide various internet services to their customers. In this paper we have provided the various internet services provided by the banks. Literature of various authors has been presented in this paper. It is concluded that for proper use of internet services a bank should provide a attractive and easy to use interface. Proper security concerns should be provided by the banks to the customers so that customers can easily use the these internet services provided by the banks. ⁽³⁾

Gupta Vijay Prakash, Agarwal P. K.(2013), The Researcher found in their research the highest customer satisfaction is demonstrated in the responsiveness area such as willingness to help customer, friendly attitude of staff, followed by the reliability area such as customer guidance, customer support and other hand, the moderate satisfactions are in the tangibles area, such as infrastructure facilities,

decor, followed by empathy area such as banks business timing and return on investment. ⁽⁴⁾

Salma Umma, Shahneaz Mir Abdullah (2013), Analysis shows that customer satisfaction vary according to the nature of the services and in this case, highest customer satisfaction is shown in such areas like price charged by banks is nominal, convenient location of bank branches and staff attitude toward problem solving of customers. When the private sector banks are compared with public sector banks, private bank customers were more satisfied with their bank because of their multiple branches at convenient locations and technology (like check deposit machines, utility bill accepting machines etc.) which were not even seen in public sector banks. But when we talk about public sector banks customers of public sector banks were more satisfied with reputation, reliability and the prices which public sector banks impose on services like cheque/cash deposit and cheque/cash withdraw (it has been shown that price charges are lower in public sector banks than in private sector).. ⁽⁵⁾

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The Research made with various purposes keeping in mind. Research has some main purpose also which are as follows:

- To identify customer Satisfaction from Banking Services.
- To identify the most services avail by banking customers.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is purely based upon the primary information's obtained from the banking customers of different areas of Uttarakhand. There were 50 banking customers, who responded well the all information's containing in the questionnaire. Questionnaire to get the satisfaction levels of customers of banks in various terms. Questionnaire design after the reasonable review received from some customers of various Banks. Questionnaire consists of 13 service related questions. Some information also collected relate to demographical information of the respondent. It is designed to observe the satisfaction of various customers from various services of Public and Private sector Banks.

Sample Design and Data Collection

- This study based on primary data.
- Primary data collected through questionnaire.
- Questionnaire collected from 50 peoples of Uttarakhand.

Questionnaire Design

Questionnaire design after the reasonable review received from some customers of various Banks. Questionnaire consists of 13 service related questions. Some different question also includes relating to demographical information of the respondent. It is designed to observe the satisfaction of various customers from various services of Banks.

V. DATA ANALYSES

Classification of the respondents according to Bank Account Type

Account Type	No of Respondents	% of Total Respondent
Saving Account	43	86%
Current Account	7	14%
Sukanya samriddhi A/C	0	0%
PPF	0	0%
Total	50	100%

(Source: Primary data)

In the total collection of data 86% customers have saving bank a/c and 14% customer has current bank a/c.

Five point likert’s scale and Percentage of Customer satisfaction on Individual Banking Services

	Service or Facility name	Customer Satisfaction Level	
		Five point likert’s scale	Percentage
1	Availability of Forms	4.06	81.2%
2	Help provided by the staff in filling forms	3.62	72.4%
3	Passbook and Bank statement Printing Facility	3.74	74.8%
4	ATM Card, Passbook, Cheque Book distribution service	4.08	81.6%
5	Secured Bank transaction	4.1	82%
6	Cash deposit and cash withdrawal waiting line is Justified	3.34	66.8%
7	Providing service within reasonable Time	3.62	72.4%
8	ATM Machines availability and cash available in machine	3.88	77.6%
9	Bank Branch infrastructure	4.04	80.8%
10	Parking facility	3.4	68%
11	Service charge	2.72	54.4%
12	Behavior of Bank staff	3.42	68.4%
13	Safety in the Bank	3.96	79.2%
Average mean of all services		3.69	73.80%

All above likert’s scale show satisfaction level out of 5 scales by using five point likert’s scale and Overall satisfaction of banks customer is 73.80%.

It was an attempt to study customer service from thirteen different dimensions. Dimensions included Availability of Forms, Help provided by the staff in filling forms, Passbook and Bank statement Printing Facility,

VI. CONCLUSION

ATM Card, Passbook, Cheque Book distribution service, Secured Bank transaction, Cash deposit and cash withdrawal waiting line is Justified, Providing service within reasonable Time, ATM Machines availability and cash available in Machine, Bank Branch infrastructure, Parking facility, Service charge, Behavior of Bank staff, Safety in the Bank and satisfaction level of customers belonging to different types of accounts, account holding time, gender, occupation, marital status, age group, Qualification. In our respondents, 86% of customers have saving bank A/C

On the basis of the analysis, it is concluded that the customer satisfaction level on service of banks is 73.80%.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ramachandhirana. (2018). Customer satisfaction: a study with Special reference to hdfc bank in tirupattur, vellore district. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 5(4), 43-50.
- [2] Herath H.M.A.K. & herath H.M.S.P. (2019). Impact of green banking initiatives on customer satisfaction: A conceptual model of customer satisfaction on green banking. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 21(1), 24-35
- [3] Singh Inder Pal & Bassi Payal. (2017). A review on customer satisfaction with internet banking in public and private bank. *International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology*, 6(1), 448-452.
- [4] Dr. Meenakshi Bindal, Dr. Bhuwan Gupta, & Sweety Dubey. (2019). Role of startups on Indian economy. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, 8(5), 142-145.
- [5] Gupta Vijay Prakash & Agarwal P.K. (2013). Comparative study of customer satisfaction in public sector and private sector banks in India(A case study of Meerut region of U.P). *International Journal of Management*, 1(1), 56-63.
- [6] Salma Umma & Shahneaz Mir Abdullah. (2013). Customer satisfaction: A comparative analysis of public and private sector banks in Bangladesh. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(4), 1-7.